

Proposal

LISS panel grant 2023

Title: Probing the causal pathways between police procedural justice and perceptions of police legitimacy using experimental vignettes

1 Layperson summary

To what extent can a single interaction with the police shape how people feel about the police? How do we know for sure it's about how police treat people, and not something else about the situation? And why might respectful treatment motivate people to comply? Previous research has focused primarily on the impact of extreme police behaviors in shaping public attitudes, with most studies conducted in the United States. This project aims to unpack how and why certain police behaviors during a routine interaction can change people's attitudes in the Dutch context. Using vignettes that depict an interaction during a routine traffic stop, combined with additional follow-up questions and open-text answers, we will be able to evaluate both the effects and underlying mechanisms that connect police behavior and individual attitudes.

2 Background of the study and relationship to the literature

According to procedural justice [PJ] theory, when police treat people in a fair, respectful, and neutral manner, individuals are more likely to perceive the police as legitimate and comply with directives (Tyler, 2006). Two mechanisms are generally provided to explain this relationship (Trinkner et al., 2018). The first is based on normative expectations about authorities, whereby PJ communicates that police authority is valid, unbiased and entitled to be obeyed. The second is rooted in social identity perspectives, whereby fair treatment communicates that individuals have status and value, strengthening the social bonds between the individual and group. PJ treatment is said to consist of two main dimensions regarding the quality of treatment (i.e., respect, trustworthy motives) and decision-making (i.e., neutral, allows voicing opinions). While experimental vignettes are increasingly used to evaluate the factors that influence individual judgements about police, the majority of these have been conducted in the United States. These vignettes have been used to depict situations in which an officer interacts with an individual, often manipulating the degree to which the officer treats the subject in a procedurally just manner (e.g., disrespectful vs respectful treatment).

Despite the growth in use of experimental vignettes to test PJ theory, there has been little to no attention to assessing the underlying causal assumptions, mechanisms and possible confounding pathways between police treatment and attitudinal outcomes (Nivette et al., 2022). Recent methodological research has shown that the design of experimental vignettes may determine to what extent causal inferences can be made (Dafoe et al., 2018). One important causal assumption is that of

information equivalence (IE) (also known as “information leakage” or “excludability”). IE refers to the notion that the effect runs *only* through the treatment (i.e., manipulation), and *not* through some other pathway. In relation to PJ, the manipulation of police behavior may influence how respondents perceive background characteristics about the subjects portrayed in the scenario. Updating beliefs about these characteristics can lead to imbalance on background beliefs between respondents, potentially confounding the relationship (e.g., see Metcalfe & Pickett, 2021).

Potential violations should be explicitly tested by including follow-up questions (placebo tests) that ask respondents about their beliefs regarding the background attributes of the subjects in the scenario. In relation to police-citizen interactions, this could be the vignette subject’s criminal history, ethnicity, or the officer’s reputation. Another promising way to learn about the mechanisms connecting police treatment and attitudinal outcomes is to ask participants what led to their selection. By prompting participants to describe this in free text, a wide array of emotions, assumptions, or other mechanisms may emerge. Related research has called for eliciting written accounts alongside survey or experiment responses, which can subsequently be categorized and analyzed using natural language processing methods (Kleinberg, van der Vegt, & Mozes, 2020; Roberts et al., 2014). This means that there are concerns regarding the internal validity of existing vignette studies testing PJ theory. The LISS panel offers the opportunity to probe these causal assumptions and mechanisms and test the theory in the Dutch context.

3 Research questions

This study aims to answer three questions:

1. To what extent do dimensions of PJ displayed during an interaction lead to greater perceptions of police legitimacy?
2. Given a typical scenario, do people update their beliefs about background attributes of the subject and officer?
3. To what extent do the open text responses correspond to the causal mechanisms according to PJ theory?

In order to answer these questions, this study will field a between-subjects vignette with a 3x2x2 factorial design. The content of the vignette will aim to replicate similar interactions as reported in previous research (i.e., a traffic stop by police), but adapted to the Dutch context (Terpstra & van Wijck, 2023). The scenario depicts a man driving his scooter to work when he is stopped by police for a vehicle inspection.

Follow-up placebo questions will ask respondents about the likelihood of certain background attributes within the scenario. To investigate the theoretical mechanisms (e.g., respect, neutrality), respondents will also be asked to what extent they would rate the interaction in terms of PJ elements. The inclusion of open-ended questions allows participants to mention reasons that led to their selections, including those that have not been explicitly prompted in the follow-up questions. For example, text responses may reveal emotions that led participants to select a specific option. Responses will be analyzed using computational linguistic methods, including sentiment analysis and structural topic models, which are commonly used to analyze open-ended survey responses (Roberts et al., 2014). The results will be able to shed light on whether and to what extent respondents update their beliefs about background attributes, and what mechanisms are driving the relationship between PJ and legitimacy. The research questions, design, and variables will be pre-registered prior to data collection.

4 Methodological approach

Requested sample size:

A sample of 2100 will be requested. A sample with $n=175$ per condition ($n\text{ total}=2100$) has sufficient power to detect main effects of each element of PJ, 2-way and 3-way interaction effects between PJ elements, and marginal contrasts. Expected means for each condition were based on previous research as well as reviews of experimental vignettes on PJ, which typically see relatively large effects ($d>1.0$) between (extreme) negative and positive conditions, although field experiments detect

much more modest effects ($d=.21$). Sensitivity analyses show that the smallest effect of interest for the two-level factors would be $d=.15$ ($n=1050$ each), and $d=.19$ contrasting two levels of the three-level factor ($n=700$ each). Although interactions between these elements have not been directly tested, based on theory one would expect that each element produces an additive effect on legitimacy. However, reviews of evidence from PJ vignettes suggests that respect may play a stronger role in shaping legitimacy beliefs compared to trustworthiness or voice (Nivette et al., 2022). The R code and G*Power protocol for all power analyses are provided in Section 6.4.

Sample composition:

We will request a representative sample of adults.

Desired timing of the fieldwork:

Spring if possible, however we do not have a strong preference.

Repeated measurements (where applicable):

N/A

Use of existing LISS panel data:

Existing information about demographic characteristics of participants will be used to conduct balance checks. Prior studies that have measured attitudes towards the police can also be used to explore additional questions about how pre-existing attitudes shape how individuals interpret interactions and make judgements about police behavior.

If applying for the extension of the LISS panel data with the CBS microdata: What is the empirical strategy and what CBS microdata do you intend to use?

N/A

5 Implications for research, practice and/or society

Generally, experimental vignettes are beneficial in that they can address several threats to internal validity and improve our understanding of factors that shape public opinion in the real world (Hainmuller et al., 2015). This study aims to make both substantive and methodological contributions to research on attitudes towards police and experimental vignettes, respectively. Substantively, this study will contribute to understanding how different elements of PJ and other situational factors may influence perceptions of police legitimacy. Positive perceptions of police legitimacy have been associated with greater willingness to cooperate with and call the police (Kochel et al., 2013). Prior research has not evaluated these effects separately in an experimental setting, as most studies either combine all elements together or focus particularly on (dis)respect (Nivette et al., 2022). In addition, previous experimental vignettes portrayed PJ at two extremes, which may not reflect real world interactions. The use of open-ended responses also allows us to probe these potential underlying pathways further compared to a typical survey. The richness of open-ended text responses has not previously been explored in experimental vignettes on attitudes towards police. The addition of computational linguistic analysis of these responses will add to the growing body of research utilizing mixed methods to gather insight on human states, traits, and attitudes through different modalities (e.g., Mozes, van der Vegt, & Kleinberg, 2021). In short, this study contributes to methodological knowledge by promoting recent best-practice recommendations (e.g., placebo tests, open text responses) for evaluating causal pathways between treatment and outcome in experimental vignettes.

6 Preliminary content of the LISS panel survey questions (optional)

6.1 Design

The vignette is a between-subjects 3x2x2 factorial design. The three factors will reflect PJ dimensions of respect, trustworthy motives, and neutrality. Respect will consist of three levels to reduce the comparison of extremes: disrespect (i.e., shouting at the subject), neutral, respect (i.e., saying please, thank you). Trustworthy motives will consist of two levels in which the officer explains their motives (trustworthy) or says nothing regarding motives (none). Neutrality will consist of two levels in which the officer explains that all drivers will be stopped (neutral), or the officer says nothing and the subject notices that other drivers are not stopped (bias).

Respondents will be asked a series of follow-up questions presented to them in blocks: placebo test questions, measurement of treatment/plausibility (fairness), outcome (encounter-specific obligation, trust, compliance), and open-ended mediation/mechanism questions. Since the respondent's answers on some questions (e.g., outcome, treatment) may influence their answers on other questions, the presentation of four of these blocks of questions will be randomized: placebo questions about the subject, placebo questions about the officer, treatment, and outcome.

Experimental vignettes will be randomized so that each subject views only one version (out of 12 possible versions). Each respondent will have an equal chance of viewing each vignette. Survey question blocks will be randomized (4 blocks) so that each respondent will have equal chance of being assigned to each of the 24 possible block order permutations.

6.2 Measures

Note: Measures and vignettes are provided in English, but we will translate into Dutch.

The following questions will ask you about what you think about the actors described in the scenario are like.

Block 1: randomize (placebo tests, vignette subject)

1. How likely is it that **Den** in the scenario is a teenager (aged 15-19)?

- Very Unlikely (0-20% chance)
- Unlikely (21-40% chance)
- Chances About Even (41-60% chance)
- Likely (61-80% chance)
- Very Likely (81-100% chance)

2. How likely is it that **Den** in the scenario has a native Dutch background?

- Very Unlikely (0-20% chance)
- Unlikely (21-40% chance)
- Chances About Even (41-60% chance)
- Likely (61-80% chance)
- Very Likely (81-100% chance)

3. How likely is it that **Den** in the scenario has a non-Western migration background?

- Very Unlikely (0-20% chance)
- Unlikely (21-40% chance)
- Chances About Even (41-60% chance)
- Likely (61-80% chance)
- Very Likely (81-100% chance)

4. How likely do you think it is that **Den** has been stopped by police prior to this interaction?

- Very Unlikely (0-20% chance)
- Unlikely (21-40% chance)
- Chances About Even (41-60% chance)
- Likely (61-80% chance)
- Very Likely (81-100% chance)

5. How likely do you think it is that **Den** has a history of other criminal offending?

- Very Unlikely (0-20% chance)
- Unlikely (21-40% chance)
- Chances About Even (41-60% chance)
- Likely (61-80% chance)
- Very Likely (81-100% chance)

Block 2: randomize (placebo tests, police)

6. How likely do you think it is that **the officer** in the scenario has a native Dutch background?

- Very Unlikely (0-20% chance)
- Unlikely (21-40% chance)
- Chances About Even (41-60% chance)
- Likely (61-80% chance)
- Very Likely (81-100% chance)

7. How likely do you think it is that **the officer** in the has a non-Western migration background?

- Very Unlikely (0-20% chance)
- Unlikely (21-40% chance)
- Chances About Even (41-60% chance)
- Likely (61-80% chance)
- Very Likely (81-100% chance)

8. How much experience do you think **the officer** has, in terms of years on the job?

- Very little experience (less than 1 year)
- Some experience (between 1-5 years)
- More experienced (6-15 years)
- Very experienced (16+ years)

9. How likely do you think it is that **this officer** has prior complaints made against him?

- Very Unlikely (0-20% chance)
- Unlikely (21-40% chance)
- Chances About Even (41-60% chance)
- Likely (61-80% chance)
- Very Likely (81-100% chance)

10. How likely do you think it is that **the police team in this area** have prior complaints made against them?

- Very Unlikely (0-20% chance)
- Unlikely (21-40% chance)
- Chances About Even (41-60% chance)
- Likely (61-80% chance)
- Very Likely (81-100% chance)

11. How likely do you think it is that this interaction took place in a wealthy neighborhood?

- Very Unlikely (0-20% chance)
- Unlikely (21-40% chance)
- Chances About Even (41-60% chance)
- Likely (61-80% chance)
- Very Likely (81-100% chance)

Block 3 (mechanisms): randomize

Think about how the police officer interacted with **Den** in the scenario.

12. The police officer in the scenario acted in a neutral and unbiased fashion.
 - Strongly agree
 - Agree
 - Neither agree nor disagree
 - Disagree
 - Strongly disagree
13. The police officer in the scenario was clearly concerned with **Den's** well-being.
 - Strongly agree
 - Agree
 - Neither agree nor disagree
 - Disagree
 - Strongly disagree
14. The police officer in the scenario listened to what **Den** had to say.
 - Strongly agree
 - Agree
 - Neither agree nor disagree
 - Disagree
 - Strongly disagree
15. The police officer in the scenario treated **Den** with dignity and respect.
 - Strongly agree
 - Agree
 - Neither agree nor disagree
 - Disagree
 - Strongly disagree

Block 4 (outcome variables, elements of police legitimacy: obligation to obey, normative alignment, trust): randomize

16. You would feel compelled to do what the police officer in the scenario asked you.
 - Strongly agree
 - Agree
 - Neither agree nor disagree
 - Disagree
 - Strongly disagree
17. Open-ended: why did you select the answer choice in the previous section?
18. You should support the decisions of police officers even when you disagree with them.
 - Strongly agree
 - Agree
 - Neither agree nor disagree
 - Disagree
 - Strongly disagree
19. Open-ended: why did you select the answer choice in the previous section?
20. The police in my community care about the people in my community.
 - Strongly agree
 - Agree
 - Neither agree nor disagree
 - Disagree
 - Strongly disagree

21. Open-ended: why did you select the answer choice in the previous section?
22. The police in my community have the same sense of right and wrong as me.
- Strongly agree
 - Agree
 - Neither agree nor disagree
 - Disagree
 - Strongly disagree
23. Open-ended: why did you select the answer choice in the previous section?
24. I trust the police.
- Strongly agree
 - Agree
 - Neither agree nor disagree
 - Disagree
 - Strongly disagree
25. Open-ended: why did you select the answer choice in the previous section?

6.3 Vignette scenarios

3x2x2 factorial design
Respect, neutral, disrespect
Trustworthy motives, none
Neutrality, bias

Respect (neutral), trustworthy (none), neutrality (bias)

Den is driving his scooter to work when he sees a police traffic control ahead of him. As he reaches the traffic control, an officer flags him to stop.

A male police officer approaches Den's scooter and says, "I just saw you driving at least 40kmph without a helmet. Can I see your license and insurance?"

Den gives him the documents, and the officer begins the inspection of his scooter for defects and places the scooter on a 'rollertestbank' to check for its top speed.

After a short time, the officer says, "I am writing you a ticket. This scooter has been tuned up to 45kmph, and you were not wearing a helmet. You will receive fines for these violations, and you are not allowed to ride your scooter until you have it officially inspected. If you want to make a statement, say it now otherwise sign the ticket and you can go."

Den signs the ticket. When he continues to work, he notices that other scooters are not being stopped.

Respect (neutral), trustworthy (none), neutral (positive)

Den is driving his scooter to work when he sees a police traffic control ahead of him. As he reaches the traffic control, an officer flags him to stop.

A male police officer approaches Den's scooter and says, "We are conducting inspections on all scooters today. I just saw you driving at least 40kmph without a helmet. Can I see your license and insurance?"

Den gives him the documents, and the officer begins the inspection of his scooter for defects and places the scooter on a 'rollertestbank' to check for its top speed.

After a short time, the officer says, "I am writing you a ticket. This scooter has been tuned up to 45kmph, and you were not wearing a helmet. You will receive fines for these violations, and you are not allowed to ride your scooter until you have it officially inspected. If you want to make a statement, say it now otherwise sign the ticket and you can go."

Den signs the ticket and continues to work.

Respect (neutral), trustworthy (pos), neutral (bias)

Den is driving his scooter to work when he sees a police traffic control ahead of him. As he reaches the traffic control, an officer flags him to stop.

A male police officer approaches Den's scooter and says, "We are conducting inspections on all scooters today. I just saw you driving at least 40kmph without a helmet. Can I see your license and insurance?"

Den gives him the documents, and the officer begins the inspection of his scooter for defects and places the scooter on a 'rollertestbank' to check for its top speed.

After a short time, the officer says, "I am writing you a ticket. This scooter has been tuned up to 45kmph, and you were not wearing a helmet. You will receive fines for these violations, and you are not allowed to ride your scooter until you have it officially inspected. If you want to make a statement, say it now otherwise sign the ticket and you can go."

As Den signs the ticket, the officer says, "Listen, every year, people die on these roads from speeding and we're just trying to keep that from happening. Our goal is to keep the roads safe by making sure everyone follows the rules."

When Den continues to work, he notices that other scooters are not being stopped.

Respect (neutral), trustworthy (positive), neutral (pos)

Den is driving his scooter to work when he sees a police traffic control ahead of him. As he reaches the traffic control, an officer flags him to stop.

A male police officer approaches Den's scooter and says, "We are conducting inspections on all scooters today. I just saw you driving at least 40kmph without a helmet. Can I see your license and insurance?"

Den gives him the documents, and the officer begins the inspection of his scooter for defects and places the scooter on a 'rollertestbank' to check for its top speed.

After a short time, the officer says, "I am writing you a ticket. This scooter has been tuned up to 45kmph, and you were not wearing a helmet. You will receive fines for these violations, and you are not allowed to ride your scooter until you have it officially inspected. If you want to make a statement, say it now otherwise sign the ticket and you can go."

As Den signs the ticket, the officer says, "Listen, every year, people die on these roads from speeding and we're just trying to keep that from happening. Our goal is to keep the roads safe by making sure everyone follows the rules."

Den continues to work.

Respect (positive), trustworthy (positive), neutral (bias)

Den is driving his scooter to work when he sees a police traffic control ahead of him. As he reaches the traffic control, an officer flags him to stop.

A male police officer approaches Den's scooter and says, "Hello, my name is Officer Janssen. I just saw you driving at least 40kmph without a helmet. Can I please see your license and insurance?"

Den gives him the documents, and the officer begins the inspection of his scooter for defects and places the scooter on a 'rollertestbank' to check for its top speed.

After a short time, the officer says, "I am writing you a ticket. This scooter has been tuned up to 45kmph, and you were not wearing a helmet. You will receive fines for these violations, and you are not allowed to ride your scooter until you have it officially inspected. If you want to make a statement, say it now otherwise please sign the ticket and you can go."

As Den signs the ticket, the officer says, "Listen, every year, people die on these roads from speeding and we're just trying to keep that from happening. Our goal is to keep the roads safe by making sure everyone follows the rules. Thanks for your cooperation."

When Den continues to work, he notices that other scooters are not being stopped.

Respect (positive), trustworthy (none), neutral (bias)

Den is driving his scooter to work when he sees a police traffic control ahead of him. As he reaches the traffic control, an officer flags him to stop.

A male police officer approaches Den's scooter and says, "Hello, my name is Officer Janssen. I just saw you driving at least 40kmph without a helmet. Can I please see your license and insurance?"

Den gives him the documents, and the officer begins the inspection of his scooter for defects and places the scooter on a 'rollertestbank' to check for its top speed.

After a short time, the officer says, "I am writing you a ticket. This scooter has been tuned up to 45kmph, and you were not wearing a helmet. You will receive fines for these violations, and you are not allowed to ride your scooter until you have it officially inspected. If you want to make a statement, say it now otherwise please sign the ticket and you can go."

The officer says thank you. As Den continues to work, he notices that other scooters are not being stopped.

Respect (positive), trustworthy (pos), neutral (bias)

Den is driving his scooter to work when he sees a police traffic control ahead of him. As he reaches the traffic control, an officer flags him to stop.

A male police officer approaches Den's scooter and says, "Hello, my name is Officer Janssen. I just saw you driving at least 40kmph without a helmet. Can I please see your license and insurance?"

Den gives him the documents, and the officer begins the inspection of his scooter for defects and places the scooter on a 'rollertestbank' to check for its top speed.

After a short time, the officer says, "I am writing you a ticket. This scooter has been tuned up to 45kmph, and you were not wearing a helmet. You will receive fines for these violations, and you are not allowed to ride your scooter until you have it officially inspected. If you want to make a statement, say it now otherwise please sign the ticket."

As Den signs the ticket, the officer says, "Listen, every year, people die on these roads from speeding and we're just trying to keep that from happening. Our goal is to keep the roads safe by making sure everyone follows the rules. Thanks for your cooperation."

The officer says thank you. As Den continues to work, he notices that other scooters are not being stopped.

Respect (positive), trustworthy (none), neutral (pos)

Den is driving his scooter to work when he sees a police traffic control ahead of him. As he reaches the traffic control, an officer flags him to stop.

A male police officer approaches Den's scooter and says, "Hello, my name is Officer Janssen, we are conducting inspections on all scooters today. I just saw you driving at least 40kmph without a helmet. Can I please see your license and insurance?"

Den gives him the documents, and the officer begins the inspection of his scooter for defects and places the scooter on a 'rollertestbank' to check for its top speed.

After a short time, the officer says, "I am writing you a ticket. This scooter has been tuned up to 45kmph, and you were not wearing a helmet. You will receive fines for these violations, and you are not allowed to ride your scooter until you have it officially inspected. If you want to make a statement, say it now otherwise please sign the ticket."

The officer says thank you and Den continues to work.

Respect (negative), trustworthy (none), neutral (bias)

Den is driving his scooter to work when he sees a police traffic control ahead of him. As he reaches the traffic control, an officer flags him to stop.

A male police officer approaches Den's scooter and says, "Are you out of your damned mind driving like that? I just saw you driving at least 40kmph without a helmet. What, are you trying to kill somebody? Get off and give me your license and insurance!"

Den gives him the documents, and the officer begins the inspection of his scooter for defects and places the scooter on a 'rollertestbank' to check for its top speed.

After a short time, the officer says, "I am writing you a ticket. This scooter has been tuned up to 45kmph, and you were not wearing a helmet. You're lucky I don't confiscate your license! You will receive fines for these violations, and you are not allowed to ride your scooter until you have it officially inspected. If you want to make a statement, say it now otherwise sign the ticket and you can go."

Den signs the ticket. When he continues to work, he notices that other scooters are not being stopped.

Respect (negative), trustworthy (none), neutral (pos)

Den is driving his scooter to work when he sees a police traffic control ahead of him. As he reaches the traffic control, an officer flags him to stop.

A male police officer approaches Den's scooter and says, "Are you out of your damned mind driving like that? I just saw you driving at least 40kmph without a helmet. What, are you trying to kill somebody? We are conducting inspections on all scooters today, so get off and give me your license and insurance!"

Den gives him the documents, and the officer begins the inspection of his scooter for defects and places the scooter on a 'rollertestbank' to check for its top speed.

After a short time, the officer says, "I am writing you a ticket. This scooter has been tuned up to 45kmph, and you were not wearing a helmet. You're lucky I don't confiscate your license! You will receive fines for these violations, and you are not allowed to ride your scooter until you have it officially inspected. If you want to make a statement, say it now otherwise sign the ticket and you can go."

Den signs the ticket and continues to work.

Respect (negative), trustworthy (pos), neutral (bias)

Den is driving his scooter to work when he sees a police traffic control ahead of him. As he reaches the traffic control, an officer flags him to stop.

A male police officer approaches Den's scooter and says, "Are you out of your damned mind driving like that? I just saw you driving at least 40kmph without a helmet. What, are you trying to kill somebody? Get off and give me your license and insurance!"

Den gives him the documents, and the officer begins the inspection of his scooter for defects and places the scooter on a 'rollertestbank' to check for its top speed.

After a short time, the officer says, "I am writing you a ticket. This scooter has been tuned up to 45kmph, and you were not wearing a helmet. **You're lucky I don't confiscate your license!** You will receive fines for these violations, and you are not allowed to ride your scooter until you have it officially inspected. If you want to make a statement, say it now otherwise sign the ticket."

As Den signs the ticket, the officer says, **"Listen, every year, people die on these roads from speeding and we're just trying to keep that from happening. Our goal is to keep the roads safe by making sure everyone follows the rules."**

As Den continues to work, **he notices that other scooters are not being stopped.**

Respect (negative), trustworthy (pos), neutral (bias)

Den is driving his scooter to work when he sees a police traffic control ahead of him. As he reaches the traffic control, an officer flags him to stop.

A male police officer approaches Den's scooter and says, **"Are you out of your damned mind driving like that? I just saw you driving at least 40kmph without a helmet. What, are you trying to kill somebody? Get off and give me your license and insurance!"**

Den gives him the documents, and the officer begins the inspection of his scooter for defects and places the scooter on a 'rollertestbank' to check for its top speed.

After a short time, the officer says, "I am writing you a ticket. This scooter has been tuned up to 45kmph, and you were not wearing a helmet. **You're lucky I don't confiscate your license!** You will receive fines for these violations, and you are not allowed to ride your scooter until you have it officially inspected. If you want to make a statement, say it now otherwise sign the ticket."

After Den signs the ticket, the officer says, **"Listen, every year, people die on these roads from speeding and we're just trying to keep that from happening. Our goal is to keep the roads safe by making sure everyone follows the rules."**

As Den continues to work, **he notices that other scooters are not being stopped.**

6.4 R Code and protocol for power analyses

Sensitivity analyses in G*Power (2-level contrasts, n=1050 per condition)

t tests – Means: Difference between two independent means (two groups)

Analysis:Sensitivity: Compute required effect size

Input:	Tail(s)	=	Two
	α err prob	=	0.05
	Power (1- β err prob)	=	0.95
	Sample size group 1	=	1050
	Sample size group 2	=	1050
Output:	Noncentrality parameter δ	=	3.6064688
	Critical t	=	1.9610954
	Df	=	2098
	Effect size d	=	0.1573992

Sensitivity analyses in G*Power (3-level contrasts, n=700 per condition)

t tests - Means: Difference between two independent means (two groups)

Analysis:Sensitivity: Compute required effect size

Input:	Tail(s)	=	Two
	α err prob	=	0.05
	Power (1- β err prob)	=	0.95
	Sample size group 1	=	700
	Sample size group 2	=	700
Output:	Noncentrality parameter δ	=	3.6072967
	Critical t	=	1.9616623
	Df	=	1398
	Effect size d	=	0.1928181

R code for interaction effects

```
install.packages("Superpower")
library("Superpower")

#3x2x2 design
labelnames <- c("Resp", "neg", "neutr", "pos", "Trust", "none", "pos",
               "Voice", "neutr", "pos") #
design_result <- ANOVA_design(design = "3b*2b*2b",
                             #sample size per group
                             n = 175,
                             #pattern of means
                             mu = c(2,2.5,2.5,3,3,3.5,3.5,4,3,3.5,3.5,4.5),
                             sd = .5, #standard deviation
                             labelnames = labelnames)

simulation_result <- ANOVA_power(design_result,
                                 alpha_level = 0.05,
                                 nsims = 10000,
                                 verbose = FALSE)

simulation_result
```

6.5 References

- Dafoe, A., Zhang, B., & Caughey, D. (2018). Information equivalence in survey experiments. *Political Analysis*, 26(4), 399–416.
- Hainmueller, J., Hangartner, D., & Yamamoto, T. (2015). Validating vignette and conjoint survey experiments against real-world behavior. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 112(8), 2395–2400.
- Kleinberg, B., van der Vegt, I., & Mozes, M. (2020). Measuring emotions in the COVID-19 real world worry dataset. In *Proceedings of the 1st workshop on NLP for COVID-19 at the 2020 Association for Computational Linguistics Conference*.
- Kochel, T.R., Parks, R., & Mastrofski, S.D. (2013). Examining police effectiveness as a precursor to legitimacy and cooperation with police. *Justice Quarterly*, 30(5), 895-925.
- Metcalf, C., & Pickett, J. T. (2021). Public fear of protesters and support for protest policing: An experimental test of two theoretical models. *Criminology*, 30.
- Mozes, M., van der Vegt, I., & Kleinberg, B. (2021). A repeated-measures study on emotional responses after a year in the pandemic. *Scientific reports*, 11(1), 23114.
- Nivette, A., Nägel, C., & Stan, A. (2022). The use of experimental vignettes in studying police procedural justice: a systematic review. *Journal of Experimental Criminology*, 1-36.
- Roberts, M. E., Stewart, B. M., Tingley, D., Lucas, C., Leder-Luis, J., Gadarian, S. K., ... & Rand, D. G. (2014). Structural topic models for open-ended survey responses. *American Journal of Political Science*, 58(4), 1064-1082.
- Terpstra, B. L., & van Wijck, P. W. (2023). The influence of police treatment and decision-making on perceptions of procedural justice: a Field Study. *Journal of research in crime and delinquency*, 60(3), 344-377.
- Trinkner, R., Jackson, J., & Tyler, T. R. (2018). Bounded authority: Expanding “appropriate” police behavior beyond procedural justice. *Law and human behavior*, 42(3), 280.
- Tyler, T. R. (2006). *Why people obey the law*. Princeton University Press.